

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON STUDY HABITS AMONG HIGHERSECONDARY STUDENTS OF GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS IN KAKCHING DISTRICT

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Introduction

Happiness, efficiency and progress in life depend on the cultivation of good habits. Good habits are an asset of one's life. Habits inspire and encourage our behavior. They play very important role in the development of child. The essence of character and socialization, social and moral discipline, learning and education are habit information. Hence, it is very important for the teacher as well as for the learner that he should realize in the importance of habits and psychology helps the teacher to know the importance of habits, how habits are formed and how bad habits can be broken or eradicated.

The term habit has been defined in different ways. Psychologists called a man a "Creature of habits" and it is the second nature" (Willington). Habit is a well learned performance" (Woodworth). "Habit as the tendency of a thing to be or to do now what it was or did on some pervious occasion" (Titchner). "Habit is merely a descriptive term denoting the repetition of similar actions in similar circumstances" (Ross). Automatic response to specific situations, acquired normally as a result of repetition and learning, strictly applicable only to motor responses , but often applied more widely to habits of thought, perhaps more correctly termed attitude" (Driver).

Study can be interpreted as a planned programme of subject-matter mastery. It is essential to learning and fundamental to school life. Its chief purposes are (1) to acquire knowledge and habit which will be useful in meeting new situation, interpreting ideas. Making judgments, and creating new ideas, and in the general enrichment of life, (2) to perfect skill, and (3) to develop attitudes. The term practice refers to the repetition of an activity in order to perfect performance. Study usually is associated with reading and reference work but it is also is related to the solution of problem arising in daily life activities.

Since study requires energy, it often is regarded by pupils as distasteful. The teachers function is to help learners find ways in which their study may become as pleasant and successful as possible. Many learners need continued guidance; other than develop for themselves good study procedures that will achieve desired results. On every school level there are learners who make comments similar to the following and actually believe the truth of their statements. "I cannot study alone." "I can study best I am listening to that radio". "My best studying is done late at night". "I study best early in the morning". High School and colleges students are prone to hold these fixed ideas concerning their study habits"

Review of Related Literatures

Budhadev and Ravina (1989), studied the attitude of pupils towards various school subjects. He found that while girls showed an overall positive attitude towards various subjects, boys had a better attitude towards science subjects. The study also revealed that the high intelligent group of pupils (regardless of gender) had a better attitude towards Mathematics and English than their low Intelligence counterparts. Likewise the high SES groups of pupil were found to have a more positive attitude towards Mathematics and English than their counterparts belonging to the low SES group. Clearly, the trend is Indicative of a positive relationship between achievement and attitudes towards a specific subject or combination of subjects in the secondary school curriculum in our country.

Chelini (1991), assessed and compared the achievement of class-VII students in response of

basic understanding and skills based on a content analysis of the textual materials and opinions of experts in non-language subjects. The study revealed that the highest number of concept mastered by any student was 39 (out of 63) in science 28 (out of 38) in mathematical and 30 (out of 41) in social studies. That is to say that a majority of students who enter the secondary stage were found deficient in more than 50 percent of the basic understanding and skills tested in science, mathematics and social studies.

Amrithalingam (1991), studied parental involvement of involvement of secondary school under achievers pare in Karaikudi district of Tamil Nadu and discovered that the under achievers parents in all most all groups based on religion, caste, family status, educational qualification income and occupation had not taken interest in their children's physical and mental development and had paid little attention on inculcating in them good habit formation for studies and participation in co-curricular activities.

Agarwal *et al.* (2000), studied televiewing pattern of adolescents and its impact on their study habits and reported, 68 percent of students fell that parents imposed restrictions on them regarding the content and duration of televiewing, there was no gender or stream difference in this context. 87 percent of students watched television for less than four hours per day. Duration of televiewing was found to affect, significantly the study habits of students. Watching T.V. for more than four hours adversely affects the study habits. Interest in watching educational programme is more suitable for good study habits. More girls liked to their family members as co-views where as friends were the choices of co- viewers of the boys. Parental control for televiewing did not affect significantly the study habits of higher secondary level students.

Storm (2006), investigated, girls and boys linked to read and write different texts. It was reported that girls were enjoying reading significantly more than boys. Boys liked mostly comics and humorous in books, adventure book were girls favorite. Many boys didn't like to read aloud, even many fluent and motivated readers felt embarrassed when doing it. Students attitude towards writing was negative than reading. Boys were significantly more reluctant writers than girls.

Rationale of the Study

It is observed that despite uniform syllabus, instructional facilities, time and resources, people score differently in examination. Even if a good student has the potentiality to achieve better, may not be able to achieve as per expectation, if fails to make proper management of time, allocation of weightage to various subject, preparing notes, and the individual modes adopted for preparation of different subjects.

Higher secondary education plays a significant role in individual life. Because after lower secondary education one may go for science stream or may go for arts stream or commerce. For high achievements secondary level, students need proper guidance to utilization of their time for better prospective.

Therefore, in this study an attempt has been made to find out the study habits of high achievers in lower secondary level. Finding of this study may be helpful for others to organize or newly formulate their study habits.

Objectives of the Study

The present study is undertaken keeping the following objective in view:

1. To find out the difference on study habits between male and female highersecondary students.
2. To suggest remedial measures to improve the study habits of higher secondary students of Manipur.

Delimitation of the Study

The study has been delimited to the comparison between male and female's Study Habits of higher secondary students of Government School in Kakching District during the academic session 2019-2020.

Method of Study

This Study is based on survey method particularly normative survey research. In view of the purpose of the study-only the survey method has been considered as most appropriate.

Sample

The sample has been defined as, ‘a miniature picture of the entire group of aggregate from which population was selected,’ in other words, it is the representative proportion of the population. For the present study, the investigator has selected 200 higher secondary students of Government School in Kakching district on the basis of random sampling technique. Detailed demography of the samples is presented in the below table:

	Male	Female	Sub-Total
Science	34	58	92
Art	23	85	108
Total	57	143	200

Tools Used

For this problem entitled, ‘the major tool used was questionnaire, as it was thought to be more flexible tool for collecting both quantitative and qualitative information.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

In the present chapter, in the light of the objectives of the study, analysis and interpretation of the data will be presented item-wise analysis and interpretation will also be done and necessary statistical representation will also be provided.

Item 1: Spending Time in studies on Normal Days

	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Morning	43	75.4%	114	79.7%
Afternoon	14	24.5%	9	6.3%
Evening	28	49%	71	49.6%
Late Night	34	59.6%	73	51%

The data revealed that both male and female higher secondary students prefer to study during morning (75.4% and 79.7% respectively) and late night (59.6% and 51% respectively) followed by evening (49% and 49.6% respectively) and afternoon (24.5% and 6.3% respectively).

Item 2: Study on Sunday and Holidays

	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Studying as usual	19	33.3%	65	45%
Not Studying at all	32	56.2%	63	44%
More Extra time	6	10.5%	16	11%

The data revealed that 56.2% male and 44% female higher secondary students do not study on Sundays and holidays, 33.3% male and 45% female students study as usual and only 10.5% male and 11% female undergraduate students spent more extra time.

Item 3: Do you regularly study at same time?

	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage

Always	8	14%	28	19.5%
Generally	25	43.8%	68	47.5%
Sometimes	14	24.5%	42	29.3%
Rarely	10	17.5%	5	3.4%

The data shows that higher education students generally study at the same time (43.8% for male and 47.5% for female); followed by sometimes with 24.5% for male and 29.3% for female. Only 14% male and 19.5% female higher education students study regularly at the same time always, whereas 17.5% male and 3.4% female rarely study regularly at same time.

Item 4: Do you have an area/place where you always go to study?

	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	22	38.5%	23	16%
No	33	57.8%	10	72%

The data revealed that majority of the higher secondary education students (57.8% male and 72% female) does not have a specific place or area where they go for study; while 38.5% male and 16% female students responded that they go to specific area for study.

Item5: If you don't understand properly the lesson/concept taught in the class, you:

	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Immediately ask question	13	22.8%	30	20.9%
Never disturb the class by asking question	2	3.5%	6	4.1%
Personally meet the teacher after the class	18	31.5%	45	31.4%
Try to understood by yourself or by asking your friends	30	52.6%	71	49.6%

The study shows that 52.65% male and 49.6% female higher secondary students try to understand the lesson /concept taught in the class by oneself or by asking their friends if they do not understand properly while 31.5% male and 31.4% female personally meet the teacher after the class to understand the lesson/concept. About 22.8% male and 20.9% female undergraduate students immediately ask question to the teacher if they do not understand the lesson/concept taught in the class while 3.5% male and 4.1% female never disturb the class by asking question.

Item 6: After your classes are over, what is the nature of discussion with your friends?

	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Study matter	11	19.2%	45	31.4%
Films	6	10.5%	14	9.7%
Sports	4	7%	12	8.3%
Girl/Boy friend	3	5.2%	8	5.5%
General discussion	34	59.6%	87	60.8%
Silly talk	12	21%	34	23.7%

The data shows that 59.6% male and 60.8% female higher secondary students have general

discussions with their friends. 19.25% male and 31.4% female students have discussions on the study matter while 21% male and 23.7% female students engage themselves with silly talks. 10.5% male and 9.7% female students talks about films, 7% male and 8.3% female students about sports, and 7% male and 5.5% female students talk about their boy/girl friend.

Item 7: What is the mode/method of your study during non-class hours?

	Male		Female	
	Frequency	percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Study alone/self study	42	73.6%	78	54.5%
Study along with one friend	2	3.5%	14	9.7%
Study along with 2/3 friends	4	7%	18	12.5%
Group study	5	8.7%	31	2.6%
Study in all circumstances	6	10.5%	13	9%

Majority of the higher secondary students (73.6% male and 54.55 female) adopts self study/study alone mode/method for study during non-class hours. 8.7% male and 2.6% female prefers group study, 7% male and 12.5% female study along with 2/3 friends, 10.5% male and 9% female study in all circumstances and 3.5% male and 9.75 female study with one friend.

Item 8: What kind of Books do you read/borrow in/from the library?

	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Text books	30	52.6%	92	64.3%
Reference books	29	50.8%	79	55.2%
Story Books	5	8.7%	20	13.9%
Dissertation /Thesis	3	5.2%	8	5.5%
Journal/Magazines	10	17.5%	18	12.5%
Others	4	7%	0	0%

Data shows that majority of the students (52.6% male and 64.3% female) read/borrow text-books in/from the library followed by reference books (50.8% male and 55.2% female), 17.5% male and 12.5% female read journals and magazines, 8.7% male and 13.9% female read story books, 5.2% male and 5.5% female go through thesis/dissertation and 7% male read/borrow other books in/from the library.

Item 9: what are your leisure time activities?

	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Talking with friends/teachers	12	21%	66	46.1%
Recreational activities like Games/watching movie	40	70.1%	90	62.9%
Solve the previous doubts	5	8.7%	17	11.8%
Go to library/laboratory	4	7%	28	19.5%
Others	7	12.2%	7	4.8%

When asked about the leisure time activities the students usually engage themselves, data revealed that recreational activities like games/watching TV was the mostpopular (70.1% male and 62.9% female), followed by talking with friends/ teachers (21% male and 46.1% female), going to library/laboratory (7% male and 19.5% female), solving previous doubts (8.7% male and 11.8% female) and 12.2% male and 4.8 female had other leisure time activities than those mentioned above.

Item 10: Who have been your sources of inspiration?

	Male	Female
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	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Parents	19	33.3%	97	67.8%
School teacher	8	14%	34	23.75%
Family members and relatives	14	24.5%	52	36.3%
Classmate	7	12.25%	13	9%
Topper in class	1	1.7%	6	4.1%
Scientist and Writer	3	5.2%	9	6.2%
School	1	1.7%	2	1.3%
Great personality	14	24.5%	24	16.7%
Nobody	6	10.5%	4	2.7%
Others	7	12.2%	7	4.8%

Parents (33.3% male and 67.8% female) were the most responded answer when the higher secondary students were asked about their source of inspiration. 24.5% male and 36.3% female responded for the family members and relatives, 14% male and 23.75% female for their school teacher, 24.5% male and 16.7% female for great personalities, 12.25% male and 9% female their classmates, 5.2% male and 6.2% female scientist, 10.5% male and 2.7% female had none while 1.7% male and 4.1% female responded for the topper in class as their source of inspiration. 1.7% male and 1.3% female responded that their schools have been their source of inspiration and 12.2% male and 4.8% female responded that they do not have any one as their source of inspiration.

CONCLUSION

Study can be interpreted as a planned programme of subject-matter mastery. Many pupils are able to develop efficient study habits without receiving, any special formal training. However, these satisfactory habits may result from the use of several methods of study before satisfactory study procedures are discovered. The behavior and the work at an individual are based, to a great extent, on habit. Every one forms, improves or changes habits in the course of study. In this study investigator has made an attempt to find out the study habits of high achiever in secondary level. Finding out of this study may be helpful for others to organize or newly formulate their study habits.

REFERENCES

- Aggarwal, K. (1986), A Study of the effect of parental encouragement upon the educational development of secondary stage students. *Ph.D. Education, Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garwal University*. Cited from fifth survey of educational research, Vol. II, NCERT, New Delhi: 1988-92, p.317
- Booker, Keonya Charlyn. (2006), School Belonging and the African, American Adolescent: What do we know and where should we go. *The High School Journal*. VI. 89, Number-4, April-May 2006
- Chauhan, S.S. (1995), *Advanced Educational Psychology*, Vikash Publishing House Pvt. Ltd, Fifth Revised Edition, New Delhi.
- Deka, U. (1985), School Failure. A Casual Comparative Study of High and Low Achievers. *Ph.D. Education*. Gauhati. University.
- Dey, N. (2001). An Investigation into the study habits of high achieving students. *M. Phill Education*, Sambalpur University, Sambalpur.
- Ghalsi. P.G. (1988). A Descriptive and Experimental Study in the Field of Study Habits/Skills of Students in Secondary Schools. *Ph.D. Education*. University of Paona. Quoted from, Fifth Survey of Educational Research; 1988-092, Vol-II, NCERT, New Delhi.
- Kulshretra, P.K. (1992). The Effect of School Environment on Adjustment, Study Habits and Achievement of High School Students. Agra University, *Quoted from Fifth Survey of*

Educational Research. 1988-92, Vol. II, NCERT, New Delhi.

Richars, L.G. Richards, H.C. and Dana, C. Sheridan (1999), Predicting Success in a First Year Engineering Course: The Role of Study Habits School of Engineering and Applied Science, Curry School of Education. University of Virginia, Nov. 10-13, 1999, San Juan, Puerto Rico.

Saxena, S.K. (2005). Self-concept as Function of Socio- Economic and Cultural Setting in First Division of High School Students. *Indian Journal of Education Research*. Vol. 20 (2) Pp. 53-58. Quoted from Indian Educational Abstracts. Vol. 2, No. 1, Jan. 2002, p.52.